

THE IMPORTANCE OF FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN EXPANDING THE REVENUE BASE OF LOCAL BUDGETS AND ITS APPLICATION OPPORTUNITIES

Sharopov Dilshodjon Rakhmatullaevich

Independent Researcher, Tashkent State

University of Economics

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19887382>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 24th April 2026

Accepted: 26th April 2026

Online: 28th April 2026

KEYWORDS

local budget, revenue base, foreign experience, tax revenues, non-tax revenues, financial independence, fiscal policy, regional finance

ABSTRACT

This article examines the importance of foreign experience in expanding the revenue base of local budgets and the possibilities of its application in national practice. It analyzes revenue formation mechanisms of local budgets in developed countries, including approaches to managing tax and non-tax revenues and ensuring financial independence. Particular attention is given to adapting foreign practices to the economic and institutional conditions of Uzbekistan. Based on the study, scientifically grounded recommendations are proposed to expand the revenue base of local budgets.

In the current global economic environment, the issue of expanding the revenue base of local budgets is becoming one of the priority directions of state financial policy. The stability and financial independence of regional budgets primarily depend on the degree to which their revenue sources are diversified and effectively managed. In this regard, studying the advanced experience of developed and developing countries, as well as adapting it to the conditions of the national economy, is of significant scientific and practical importance.

Foreign experience shows that improving the tax system, increasing the role of local taxes, ensuring efficient use of state property, and diversifying non-tax revenues play a crucial role in expanding the revenue base of local budgets. In addition, the introduction of digital technologies, simplification of tax administration, and ensuring transparency contribute to the sustainable growth of budget revenues.

However, the direct application of foreign experience does not always yield effective results. It requires adaptation to the institutional characteristics, legal framework, and level of regional development of the national economy. From this perspective, the objective of this study is to assess the importance of foreign experience in expanding the revenue base of local budgets and to substantiate the possibilities of its application in the conditions of Uzbekistan.

There are general similarities between the mechanisms of local tax collection in developed countries and the current state of the economy of our Republic. These similarities lie in the fact that, in foreign countries as well, the main sources of regional financial resources are taxes and non-tax payments. However, each country also has its own specific features in the formation of centralized and regional financial resources.

In the Russian Federation, the local budget system operates through tax centralization, whereby tax authorities are granted the authority to collect and allocate funds. This is an

integral feature of tax or fiscal federalism, which involves the differentiation of financial powers, primarily expanding competencies related to tax administration and the functioning of the state budget system.

Certain patterns can be observed in the practice of federalism in Russia. In developing countries, tax systems tend to be more centralized, as central governments are reluctant to relinquish revenue sources and face difficulties in managing local taxation. This tendency is particularly evident in federal-type states. Although Russia is a federal state, it is characterized by a significant degree of centralization of fiscal powers, which is typical for many transition economies.

Practices such as maintaining real estate cadastre systems (as in France), monitoring compliance with minimum wage legislation for entrepreneurs (as in the United Kingdom), undertaking debt recovery and representation of interests, state involvement in bankruptcy proceedings (as in Sweden), monitoring the repayment of mortgage and other types of loans (in the United Kingdom, this is applied particularly to student loan repayments), financial oversight of compliance with obligations, and state participation in enterprises where a significant share of capital belongs to the state (as in Germany, and similarly in the United States where a government auditor may be appointed in private banks), as well as the administration of social benefits, can all be integrated. In essence, this generalization reflects an ideal tax system based on the most advanced global trends.

The tax system of the United States is structurally similar to that of the Republic of Uzbekistan in terms of its federal organization.

In the United States, taxes are divided into three levels based on their allocation: federal, state, and municipal budgets.

Key features include the following:

- Federal taxes are progressive in nature, meaning that as the taxable base increases, the tax rate also increases, while local taxes are often calculated using regressive rates;
- Although the U.S. tax system consists of three levels, taxes are not strictly classified in legislation as federal, state, or local; each state has the authority to establish its own taxes;
- The same types of taxes may be imposed simultaneously by federal, state, and local governments. For example, individuals may pay different types of income and property taxes to various levels of government, while companies pay corporate taxes at the federal level;
- The U.S. tax system primarily relies on direct taxation. For instance, there is no value-added tax (VAT) at the federal level, but most states impose a sales tax;
- Unlike the tax system of Uzbekistan, social security contributions are paid not only by employers but also by employees themselves;
- A significant share of tax revenues is distributed such that approximately 70% goes to the federal budget, while around 30% is allocated to state and municipal budgets.

The main taxes in the U.S. tax system include:

- Personal income tax, which serves as the primary source of federal budget revenue and is also paid by self-employed individuals;
- Property tax for individuals and companies;
- Corporate income tax;
- Excise taxes (indirect taxes);

- Sales taxes (indirect taxes);
- Payroll taxes (social security contributions);
- Taxes aimed at addressing unemployment.

Overall, the U.S. tax system generates about 30% of the country's gross domestic product. The tax burden in the United States is considered one of the lowest among industrialized countries.

The German tax system is considered complex for foreign users. This complexity is largely due to the abundance of regulations, each of which applies uniformly across the country. Economic experts associate this feature of the German system with the government's approach to taxation within the country. They regard the high tax burden as the main "guarantor" of state revenues. Since the tax system is a key component of the overall economic system, the government places significant emphasis on strict control over tax collection.

Often, local residents themselves find it difficult to fully understand the extensive tax legislation. Therefore, they rely on private specialists—tax and financial advisors, lawyers, and auditors. The main law regulating taxation in the country is called the "Tax Code," which Germans often refer to as the tax "Constitution."

Taxes in Germany are divided into three main groups:

- **Income taxes:** personal income tax and trade tax for legal entities;
- **Property taxes:** taxes on land, gifts, and inheritance;
- **Transaction and consumption taxes:** real estate transfer tax and value-added tax (VAT).

As in many countries, income tax is the main source of budget revenue in Germany (about 40%) and is calculated using progressive rates. The minimum rate is 19%, while the maximum reaches 53%. Corporate income is taxed at relatively high uniform rates—up to 45% of profits. As a result, taxes ensure the stability of a large share of budget revenues—approximately 80%.

The German budget is consolidated and structured into three levels:

- **Federal (central) budget:** receives up to 50% of total tax revenues;
- **Regional (federal states) budgets:** receive about one-third of all tax payments;
- **Local (municipal) budgets:** receive approximately 10% of collected taxes.

Similar to Germany, Italy has adopted a relatively extensive tax system. Its legal framework includes more than 350 federal laws. The fundamental principles of taxation are defined by the Italian Constitution. This European country is characterized by a high tax burden. The tax system primarily focuses on direct taxes, which account for about 40% of all tax revenues. Indirect taxes lag slightly behind, contributing around 25% of total revenues. Overall, taxes and duties guarantee more than half of the state's total income.

The Italian tax system has a two-tier structure: national (state) and local levels. Taxation is represented by approximately 40 types of taxes and duties.

The main taxes in Italy include personal income tax, VAT, and corporate income tax. These state-level taxes account for nearly 80% of total tax revenues. In addition, national taxes include:

- excise taxes;

- social security contributions;
- gambling tax;
- registration, mortgage, and cadastral duties;
- lottery tax;
- gift and inheritance taxes.

Local taxation includes:

- tax on production activities;
- property tax;
- waste disposal fees;
- insurance and registration fees for vehicle owners;
- additional excise on electricity;
- supplementary municipal taxes, among others.

Unlike the tax system of Uzbekistan, state organizations in Italy do not transfer taxes to the budget; their activities are financed without taking accrued taxes into account.

The Japanese tax system has several distinctive features compared to that of Uzbekistan. Japan is a unitary state divided into 47 prefectures and nearly 2,000 municipalities. Due to a high degree of autonomy, local authorities receive several times more tax revenues than the central government. The independence of prefectures and municipalities is закреплена in the Constitution of 1947.

Japan has a two-tier tax structure, where all taxes are divided into national and local taxes.

At the national (central government) level, the following taxes are established:

- income tax;
- corporate income tax;
- gift and inheritance tax;
- consumption tax;
- excise tax;
- state duties, among others.

As in European countries and the United States, income tax in Japan is levied using progressive rates ranging from 5% to 40%. Corporate profit is taxed at relatively high rates between 22% and 30%, increasing with higher commercial income. In addition to the base rate, capital gains tax rates ranging from 5% to 10% are also applied.

The consumption tax, similar to VAT used in developed countries such as China, is imposed on the turnover of goods, services, and works. Its rate is relatively low—about 5%.

Prefectural taxes include:

- residence tax;
- local consumption tax;
- real estate acquisition tax;
- excise taxes;
- vehicle tax, among others.

Municipal-level taxes include:

- residence tax within the municipality;
- excise taxes;

- property and land taxes;
- fuel taxes, among others.

In countries around the world, real estate is considered one of the main sources of local budget revenues. In particular, the share of this tax in municipal budgets составляет about 40% in Canada and around 30% in the United Kingdom. The practice of real estate taxation is treated as a priority task in advanced countries.

Among the Central Asian countries, the Republic of Kazakhstan has planned, starting from 2023, to transfer several types of taxes to local budgets. In this context, a number of tasks have been defined for reforming local budget relations.

In Kazakhstan, in order to strengthen the formation of local budget revenues, several new types of fees have been introduced since 2023. These include charges for the use of wildlife resources, fees for the use of specially protected natural areas of national importance, and fees related to the use of motor vehicles.

In this country, taxes also play an important role in shaping local budget revenues, ranking second after intergovernmental transfers. This can be observed in the fact that in 2023, local taxes accounted for 44.3% of local budget revenues, which is an increase of 0.4% compared to 2022.

In conclusion, it should be emphasized that despite certain advantages and disadvantages, no tax system can be categorically defined as good or bad. Each system is beneficial in its own way for the country in which it operates. The tax systems of many countries have evolved over centuries and have already been adapted to their territorial characteristics, domestic policies, and the mentality of the population. Therefore, it is not feasible to simply replace one tax system with another. Such a transformation is only effective when taxation principles are adapted to the specific economic conditions of a given country.

Furthermore, based on advanced foreign practices, it would be appropriate to allow local governments to initiate the establishment of business entities with foreign participation in their regions, with the condition that all taxes and payments made by such entities remain within the local budget. This approach would enhance the fulfillment of projected local budget revenues and improve the financing of expenditures, while also increasing the responsibility of local authorities in tax collection.

References:

- 1.Peshkova, Kh.V. Tax and budgetary federalism and its influence on the concept of the “budgetary structure of the state” // Taxes. 2014. No. 6. p. 20.
- 2.Edelev, A.L. Migration processes and regional problems in the sphere of tax relations // Taxes. 2012.
- 3.https://nalog-nalog.ru/nalogovaya_sistema_rf/nalogovaya_sistema_ssha_i_drugih_zarubezhnyh_strann/sistem
- 4.Voronin, S., Koraboev, B., Niyazmetov, I., Ugay, D. International experience in real estate taxation // Society and Economy. – 2021. – Issue 2, pp. 119–130.
- 5.https://uz.wikipedia.org/wiki/AQSh_iqtisodiyoti
- 6.<https://renessans-edu.uz>

7. Toshmatov, Sh. The role of taxes in enterprise development. Monograph. – Tashkent: Fan va texnologiya, 2008. – 204 p.
8. Groenendijk, N., Yansoo, A. Fiscal federalism in transition countries: the three Baltic states compared. Public Finance and Management, Vol. 16, No. 3, pp. 255–280, 2016.
9. Khayriddinov, A.B. Ways to ensure the stability of local budget revenue bases. Abstract of PhD dissertation. – Tashkent, 2011. p. 13.

